

IN-SERVICE TRAINING COURSE AND WORK ENVIRONMENT

CURSO DE ENTRENAMIENTO EN SERVICIO Y ENTORNO DE TRABAJO

RESUMEN

El objetivo de esta investigación fue determinar la relación entre el curso de capacitación en servicio y el ambiente de trabajo basado en el modelo de transición HOLTON (1987). Se ha utilizado un método descriptivo-analítico. Los resultados de la investigación indican que se puede considerar lo siguiente para la transferencia efectiva de la educación al ambiente de trabajo en Irán: 1) Preparación del alumno; 2) Proporcionar comentarios apropiados a los alumnos en el menor tiempo posible; 3) Crear un clima organizacional positivo y deseable.

Palabras claves: Transferencia de Aprendizaje, Medio Ambiente, Modelo de Transición Holton.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was determining the relationship between in-service training course and work environment based on HOLTON transition model (1987). A descriptive-analytical method has been used. Findings of the research indicate that the following can be considered for effective transfer of education to the work environment in Iran: 1) Readiness of the learner; 2) Provide appropriate feedback to learners in the shortest possible time; 3) Creating a positive and desirable organizational climate.

Keywords: Learning Transfer, Environment, Holton Transition Model.

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¹ Assistant Professor in Curriculum, Department of Educational Sciences, Shahed University, Tehran. Iran. Email: nourabadi@shahed.ac.ir. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6524-8240>. (Corresponding Author)

² M.A. in Curriculum, Department of Educational Sciences, Shahed University, Tehran. Iran. Email: rezvane.amini@shahed.ac.ir. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4694-1055>.

INTRODUCTION

According to the changes in knowledge and human science in the world, all sciences are evolving rapidly. Organizations interact with their environment as an open system and need to respond to environmental changes to survive. Since human resources are the most important factor of the organization, equipping and preparing human resources to face the changes is of particular importance, and all organizations, with any mission, should have assigned the greatest amount of capital, time, and program to cultivate humans in different dimensions. Abili (2015) writes:

Development of human resource in organizations has become a form of commitment and mutual expectation, and a dual task between the individual and the organization. Within the framework of this commitment and mutual expectation, employees must also define their mutual rights by demonstrating their practical commitment to carry out their duties in accordance with organizational goals as well as within the framework of their rules of procedure. The importance of these rights can be derived from the opportunity for continuous development of knowledge, skills and evolution of various aspects of personality of staff (p. 65).

Learning is the process of transferring information, attitudes and skills from one person or group to another person or group to change their cognitive, attitude and skill structures (Sadri, 2014). Learning is a term that covers a wide range of activities. The purpose of staff training is to make efforts to improve the level of knowledge and awareness, technical skills, and occupational skills, as well as to create the desired behavior in organization's staff and also prepare them for their duties and responsibilities. Staff training has a broad and wide meaning, and does not just mean internship, or practice in a particular field; but its scope is so broad that it starts with learning from a simple career and having a complete focus on extremely complex sciences and techniques, athletics in supervisory and managerial affairs in governmental, industrial, and commercial organizations, as well as how to deal adequately with human, economic, social and cultural issues.

In-service training is organizationally referred to as an educational one, after being hired by an individual in the organization, with the aim of preparing them for better responsibilities and improving their abilities and skills. In-service training started today in Western societies in the 14th century. There are many other definitions of in-service training. From these definitions one can assume that in-service training has effects:

-After hiring a person in an institution or organization.

-The aim and purpose of this training is to prepare staff for the optimal performance of their duties and responsibilities.

-These types of training are mainly based on three main axes: "Knowledge Development, Skills Improvement, and Creation or Change Attitudes".

-The main orientation of these trainings or tasks is the business (Fathi Vajargah, 2014).

This research aims to determine the relationship between in-service training course and work environment.

METHODOLOGY

According to the sources of this study, the nature of the subject matter of this research is qualitative research. Descriptive research includes a set of methods whose purpose is to describe the conditions or phenomena under investigation. "In the descriptive method, the researcher seeks to describe objective, real, and regular characteristics of a position or subject" (Naderi & Saif Naraghi, 2016, p. 25). Descriptive research can only be used to better understand the existing conditions or to assist the decision-making process (Sarmed, 2016; Razavi, Nasirian & Afkhami, 2015). The goal of analytical research is to understand and improve a set of concepts or conceptual structures in which they interpret experience, set goals, construct issues and implement research. In other words, the purpose of analytical research is to clarify the concepts and wants to give a detailed and informative picture of the nature of the concept (Short, 2015; Bahremand, 2015).

This is a qualitative research whose data were collected through a questionnaire. The population of this research is undergraduate students in Tehran universities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of effectiveness is one of the most important, most vague and at the same time the most controversial topic in the field of education (Sadri, 2014). This feature is due to ambiguities that exist in the definition and, in some cases, in its evaluation (Bahremand, 2015). Based on this, several definitions and patterns have been developed to assess the effectiveness of education. Learning transfer can be defined as the efficiency and continuity of the use of learned knowledge, skills and attitudes from trainees or learners (Upikang, 2017).

The Holton model is one of the most popular and most widely used models for **transferring education** and is known in many countries around the world as the Holton Transitional model. Education should be used for generating work and for a period of time to understand whether training or learning has been learned. So,

one of the newest models in the field of assessing the effectiveness of education is the Holton model called “Transitional Model” (Rouiller & Goldstein, 2016).

Changes in individual performance are used as learning outcomes and organizational level. Results are considered as the result of changes in individual performance. The term individual performance in the transition model has been used instead of behavior in the Kirkpatrick model (Holton, Bates & Ruona, 2019; Alpeisso, Dossanova, Baigonysova & Kozhenova, 2018).

There is an agreement, with the exception of motivation, about the impact of other personal characteristics on learning and the transfer function. In the motivation of individuals, the plurality of motivations investigated by researchers has made it difficult to categorize the results. Holton has proposed two types of motivation, and in the literature, research shows that each of them has different aspects. Individual features include a variety of trainee characteristics such as previous knowledge, general ability, skill level, motivation level, and receipts from learning resources. Individual factors are, in fact, the characteristics or factors that an intern trains within himself in a training position (Alvarez, Salas & Garofan, 2014). Individual factors include eight components: learner's readiness, transfer motivation, individual capacity for transfer, positive individual results, negative individual results, expectations from attempting to transfer, expectations from performance outcomes and performance self-efficacy (Heydari, 2016; Upikang, 2017).

Educational factors, the second group, is one of the structures that indirectly affect the transfer, directly or through the impact on learning. Educational factors collectively referred to as "Design and Provide Interventions" (Burke & Hutchins, 2014; Friedman & Ronen, 2015). Based on the transfer of educational system, the design of education is the same as the transfer scheme, which enables trained designers and translators to learners in order to return to their jobs (Holton et al., 2019). Learning factors are comprised of two components: the validity of the content and the design of the transfer (Heydari, 2016; Metsämuuronen, 2018).

Organizational characteristics are less considered by researchers than personal and educational features. First, there are few studies in this area; in addition, researchers do not agree on the coordination method for measuring organizational conditions. Investigations on the impact of organizational features on transfer have increasingly focused on factors such as organizational support, value of education for organization, management support, supervisor support, support for colleagues, and opportunity to use education (Alvarez et al. 2014). Environmental factors refer to environmental factors that affect the performance of individuals. This section relates to the impact of the learners' work environment on their transfer of education. A wide range of environmental factors that generally affects the effectiveness of education can influence the transfer of education. The variables of

organizational conditions and working environment factors can promote, prevent or reduce the transfer of education (Heydari, 2016; Man AGE Mostafavi & Surendar, 2019)

Organizational factors comprised of six components, namely: peer support, supervisor support, supervisor's punishment, application opportunity, freedom of change and performance guidance (Heydari, 2016).

The Holton model states that these three sets of features are directly related to learning and transmission performance. Such a clear connection exists because of the interaction between the features. For example, Holton states that primary characteristics (for example motivation) affect educational and organizational characteristics, and thus affect educational outcomes.

Transition model is a conceptual evaluation model focused on learner's performance and is considered as a result of learning in changing the performance of individuals. Accordingly, the results of organizational level are a result of changes in the performance of individuals. On the other hand, the transition model is a very comprehensive model that used to determine the effect of intervening variables such as motivation, environment, ability and impact of secondary factors such as self-efficacy and learner's readiness (Khorasani & Eidi, 2017; Aziz & Abdolghader, 2018).

However, this model does not consider the contribution of knowledge to transferring education, which can play a key role in learning transfer. The opportunity is used to the extent that the trainee learns to use resources that enable him to apply new skills. Holton and colleagues argued that the transfer conditions of trainees' learning were in line with organizational references such as supervisors, co-workers, and duties (Holton, Bates, Seyle & Carvalho, 2014).

Other researches in this field are mentioned which have been done in Iran. Azimi (2017) evaluates "The effectiveness of employee training courses based on the Holton model in Roham Datak Co.", with the aim of evaluating the effectiveness of staff training courses based on the Holton model in this company. The research method in this research was the descriptive method with a survey type, also applicable in terms of purpose.

Shams & Abasi (2017) in a study entitled "Pathology and the Effectiveness of Transferring Education to the Work Environment Based on the Holton Transferring Model" to the pathology and effectiveness of transferring education to the work environment. The research methodology in terms of purpose was applied. Finally, it was determined that the secondary factors, like motivational elements, environmental factors and the elements of the ability to transfer education to the work environment, were evaluated among high school humanities teachers.

Mohammadi, Naseri, Athar & Jahromi (2016) argue that nursing is one of the occupations in the field of health. In addition to providing health services, they need continuous education, in addition to personal development, they will also be aware of the latest achievements of medical science. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the factors affecting the transfer of learning from nursing in-service training to work environment based on the Holton transition model.

Nazari & Moayedi (2016), in a research entitled "Designing a Model for Assessing the Effectiveness of Staff Training Courses Based on the Holton Transition Model in Saipa Company", was designed based on the assessment design of the effectiveness of the training course based on the transition model in one of the major industrial companies.

FINDINGS

Assessing the effectiveness of courses is one of the most important and, at the same time, the most complex and challenging tasks of the educational system in all organizations and types of in-service training. This research is based on extensive library studies and the use of lecturers' opinions and guidance as well as the results of field activities including the gathering of information from the managers, supervisors, executives and employees of Saipa Company. Based on the collected data, two activities were carried out: the appropriate model was identified, modified and edited and then presented to assess the effectiveness of the training courses of the company.

The purpose of this study is to examine the factors affecting the transfer of education to the work environment based on the Holton transition model. The purpose of this research is applied and descriptive-survey research. Data analysis showed that individual and organizational factors have the greatest impact on the transfer of training in the work environment. Among the individual factors, the component of apprenticeship talent and among the organizational factors, the expected performance component of the effort to transfer have a greater impact on the transfer of training to the work environment.

In summary, by examining research done inside and outside the country, it can be concluded that the concept of effectiveness is one of the most important and, at the same time, the most controversial topic in the field of education. Based on this, several definitions and different models have been developed to assess the effectiveness of education. One of the newest models in the field of assessing the effectiveness of education is the Holton model entitled "Transitional Model." A comprehensive model, with the simple application in this research, describes its various aspects for the benefit of the education sector in various organizations in Iran, and offers clear illustration of this model for users.

CONCLUSION

The development of human resources in organizations has become a form of commitment and mutual expectation and also a two-way task between individual and organization. Within the framework of this commitment and mutual expectation, employees must also define their mutual rights by demonstrating their practical commitment to perform their duties in pursuit of organizational goals.

The most important of these rights is opportunity to use continuous development of knowledge and skills and so evolving various aspects of the personality of the staff (Abili, 2015).

The present study was a descriptive study. The results of this study showed that the individual, organizational and educational factors influencing the transfer of learning from in-service training to the work environment from the viewpoints of nurses of Jahrom University of Medical Sciences were more than average, but lower than the optimal level. It should be given special attention to the effectiveness of nurses' in-service training courses and motivation to transfer their learning experiences to the work environment.

Organizations spend a lot of time and money for training to facilitate the learning of related competencies in employees. Staff training and development not only play an important role in increasing their knowledge and skills, but also contribute to the ability of individuals to improve the level of efficiency and effectiveness of work and be able to adapt themselves to changing environmental pressures. If training can be effective, it can be transmitted to the actual work environment.

In fact, the transfer of education means the use of knowledge and findings in the field of action. The Holton transition model is one of the newest models in the literature on the effectiveness of in-service training. Holton and colleagues in the first study and the proposed model as a conceptual framework, assume three educational outcomes that affect transfer of learning.

These results include learning, individual performance and organizational outcomes. Holton model states that these three sets of features are directly related to learning and transmission performance. Such a clear connection exists because of the interaction between the features.

The basic assumption in this model is that the effectiveness of education should be measured based on the transfer of learning from the training to the actual work environment. Therefore, the factors affecting the extent of the use of training in the real work environment have evaluated the components that effect this transfer and

application of the learning. The Holton transition model can also be used for the following purposes in the country:

1. To assess the potential problems of transitional factors,
2. To evaluate educational programs,
3. To handle known transfer problems,
4. To design targeted interventions to improve transmission, and
5. To integrated transfer evaluation as part of a regular staff assessment.

Finally, if the training courses are designed in such a way that they can best emphasize the transfer of training, three components of learning, individual performance and organizational outcomes, the effectiveness of training courses will also increase. According to the research findings, the following can be considered for effective transfer of training to the work environment in the target community:

- On the readiness of the learner, the organizers of the training courses learn about the goals and function of the course correctly;
- Provide appropriate feedback to learners in the shortest time possible, and identify the criteria for evaluating learners to provide feedback;
- Create positive and desirable organizational climate between the staff in order to benefit from each other's support for the use of new learning;
- To facilitate the transfer of learning from the training courses to the work environment, staff, supervisors and managers should be given a more positive atmosphere and encouraged to use the training received from courses in their work environment.

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